

Access barriers and facilitators for health care in patients with arterial hypertension

I. Sociodemographic dimension

To Gender:

- 1. Feminine
- 2. Masculine

B Age:

- 1) 18-27 years
- 2) 28-37 years
- 3) 38-47 years
- 4) > 48 years
- 5) over 60
- 6) over 70

C. Marital Status:

- 1. Single
- 2. Cohabitant
- 3. Married
- 4. Widower
- 5. Divorced

D. Schooling

- 1. He never attended school
- 2. Elementary
- 3. Incomplete high school
- 4. Complete high school
- 5. superior technique
- 6. college senior

E. Occupation

- 1. Housewife 2. Student 3. worker 4. Employee 5. Merchant

F. employment status

- 1. Vacant 2. Pensioner 3. Independent 4. Dependent

G. Family economic income monthly number of people who contribute to the family basket.

- 1. Up to S/ 750 nuevos soles 2. From 751 to 1500 nuevos soles 3. From 1501 to 3000 4. > 3001 new

H. You have comprehensive health insurance.

- 1. Total Subsidy: You pay nothing
- 2. Semi-contributory subsidy: You acquired this insurance and pay an amount.
- 3. Independent Insurance: Purchased independent insurance
- 4. does not have sis

I. Spend on consultations for arterial hypertension (if you answer YES, specify amount)

- 2. YES
- 1. NOT

J. Amount

K. Spend on medications for high blood pressure

- 2. YES
- 1. NOT

L. Amount

M. The house where you live:

- 1. Lived on the street
- 2. Friends
- 3. Familiar
- 4. Rented
- 5. Inheritance
- 6. own

B. Availability dimension. -services, human resources, equipment, inputs, infrastructure and information

1. Do you consider the environment where you receive care comfortable and clean?
3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

2. Do you consider the hospital bathrooms clean?
3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

3. When you go to the office, do they check your blood pressure with the equipment shown in

the image?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

4. Have you ever missed care because the doctor was not available to see you?
3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

5. Would you prefer to attend the late shift?
3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

6. Did you receive timely care for your medical consultations?
3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

7. Did you receive timely attention to take control tests for your arterial hypertension?
3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

8. Do you know the laboratory service?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

9. Did you receive any information about your disease (hypertension) from health personnel?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

C. Accessibility Dimension associated with physical accessibility such as distance, connectivity, transportation time, organizational and administrative accessibility for care.

10. How long does it take from your place of residence to the hospital?

- 1. Between 0 to 20 minutes
- 2. Between 21 to 40 minutes
- 3. Between 41 to 60 minutes
- 4. more than 60 minutes

11. What means of transportation do you use to get to the hospital?

- 1. Walking
- 2. Cab
- 3. Moto-Taxi
- 4. Bicycle
- 5. Bus
- 6. Own car
- 7. Other Which one? _____

12. Do you consider that the health personnel are trained to carry out your care?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

13. Did you have any difficulties with the administrative procedures to receive care?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

14. What difficulty did you have in requesting care?

- a. Lack of information
- b. Non-authorization of the service
- c. Difficulty of time dates
- d. Personal financial aspects
- e. Service availability
- f. additional procedures
- g. Does not know
- h. None
- i. Other/ Which? _____

15. How much time elapsed from the day I requested the last appointment until the date of care by the health personnel?

- 1. 1 - 3 days
- 2. 4 - 6 days
- 3. 7- 9 days
- 4. 10-12 days
- 5. 13- 15 days
- 6. One month
- 7. More than a month
- 8. Does not know

16. On the day of your care, do you consider the time you waited adequate from the moment you made the appointment until the time of care?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

17. On the day of your appointment, how long do I wait to be seen?

- 1. Less than 30 minutes 2. From 31 minutes to 60 minutes
- 3. From 61 minutes to 120 minutes
- 4. From 121 minutes to 180 minutes 5. Further three hours (more than 180)
- 6. More than four hours (more than 240)

18. He received timely attention for his control exams

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

19. Attending the consultation means an economic loss for you since you stop receiving income for the time you spend for your care

2. YES 1. NOT

20. If the answer is affirmative, insofar as it estimates the economic loss that the demand for care due to its health problem (arterial hypertension).

Amount

21. An adult in your family group stops working to accompany you to the consultation

to. YEAH b. NO

22. . If you answered yes, how much does this person stop receiving for accompanying them to the consultation?

Amount

23. Did you make any payment for the consultation or medical service?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

24. Have you ever missed a consultation due to lack of money?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

25. Did you buy medicines for your treatment?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

26. Do you ever not take the medication because you don't have enough money to buy it?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

27. In the last year have you been denied the provision of health services?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

Acceptability

28. Were you ever afraid or ashamed of going to the hospital?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

29. Have you ever felt discriminated against or rejected because of your illness?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

30. Would it be difficult for you to let a neighbor or family member know that you have a health problem?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

31. What do you think that the prescribed treatment will control hypertension?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

32. Do you consider that the attending physician has sufficient knowledge to achieve your recovery?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

33. Do you trust the health personnel who care for you?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

34. How did you feel about the doctor's treatment?

a to excellent b good c

Regular bad

Contact

35. How satisfied are you with the quality of care in the health service?? Understanding quality as the ability of professionals to serve you satisfactorily.

5. Excellent 4. Very good 3. good 2. Regular 1. lousy

36. How satisfied are you with the quality of treatment received? Understanding quality as the technical capacity of the professional to solve your health problem

5. Excellent 4. Very good 3. good 2. Regular 1. lousy

37. Did the health personnel answer your concerns about your illness and/or treatment?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

38. Have you presented any discomfort attributable to the medication you were receiving?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

39. Did you stop taking your medications at any time before finishing treatment?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

(only if you answer YES go to the next question).

40. What were the reasons why you stopped taking the treatment?

1. Quantity and size of the drug
2. Discomfort when receiving treatment
3. Duration of treatment
4. Not feeling better
5. Ignorance of the disease
6. feel better

41. Did the health professional explain what the disease consisted of?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

42. Did the health professional explain to you what the treatment consisted of?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

43. Were you satisfied with the explanation?

3. YES 2. NOT 1. DON'T KNOW

ADHERENCE

Morisky-Green test

	YEAH	NO
1. Do you ever forget to take medicine to treat your illness?		
2. Do you take the medications at the indicated times?		
3. When you feel well, do you stop taking the medication?		
4. If you ever feel bad, do you stop taking it?		